

Squeeze Casting of Silicon Carbide Fiber Reinforced Alminum

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ABSTRACT

Squeeze casting increases the productivity of common machine parts made from metal matrix composites, whereas the theoretically predicted strength is not easily attainable due to many factors. The present investigation has been carried out systematically to find the optimum conditions for squeeze casting applied to fabrication of SiC fiber reinforced aluminum. The experiments show that the selected conditions satisfy all of the requirements, i.e. soundness and high strength.

INTRODUCTION

Inorganic-fiber-reinforced light-metal composites have high specific strength and specific elasticity, together with excellent heat resistance. The composites is promising not only for aircrafts(1,2), but also for common machine parts such as the reciprocating piston, the connecting rod, the pressure plate of vane pump etc, if the high productivity of these parts is attainable. The production method in which molten metal is forcibly charged into fiber skeleton and solidified under high pressure (hereinafter referred to as "squeeze casting"), may remedy the demerits of diffusion bonding.

The present study is systematically scheduled to find out an optimum squeeze casting condition, deals with trial manufacture of testing apparatus, and extensive productions of SiC-fiber-reinforced aluminum under various squeeze pressures, infiltration speeds and temperatures, along with material testing to evaluate the composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Continuous SiC fiber having average diameter of $13\mu\text{m}$ was used as a reinforcing fiber. Table 1 shows the properties of the mono-filament. A bundle of fibers consists of 500 single fibers in as-supplied state. The fiber was employed because it does not degrade its strength in the air up to about $1,000^\circ\text{C}$ (3), has good wettability with molten aluminum, reacts little with

Table 1 Characteristics of SiC fiber

Tensile strength	150-230 kg/mm ²	(3)
Young's modulus	18900 kg/mm ²	1)
Specific weight	2.50 g/cm ³	1)
Specific heat	0.20 cal/(g·deg)	(4)
Heat conductivity	0.05 cal/(s·cm·deg)	(4)
Coefficient of linear expansion	4.0×10^{-6} /deg	(4)

1) Measured value

molten aluminum, and is chemically stable (5,6).

Pure aluminum(99.997%Al, 0.0003%Si, 0.0002%Cu) was used as matrix metal. Aluminum was employed as a light metal material, and has good compatibility with SiC fibers, together with its wellknown properties as shown in Table 2.

Figure 1 gives an outline of the apparatus which was manufactured tentatively to prepare composite materials composed of inorganic fibers and matrix metal by means of squeeze casting. The apparatus proper is composed of an electric furnace for supplementally heating molten aluminum and a thermocouple for measuring temperatures of the inside wall of the furnace. The metal die, on the other hand, has a molded fiber support and a thermocouple for measuring die temperatures. The metal die can slide along the apparatus proper. A hydraulic press with 20t capacity applies pressures to the metal die at a maximum ram speed of 3.2cm/s, and thereby molten metal is pressed at the maximum pressure of 2,000kg/cm². The inside of the apparatus proper is stepped to minimize pressure loss due to breaking of solidified shells mechanically. The experiment for producing composite materials was carried out as follows: The temperatures of the molded-fiber-inserted metal die, molten metal and of apparatus proper were kept constant at Tf', Ta' and Tm', respectively; the metal die was mounted on the apparatus proper into which a given amount of molten aluminum had been poured in advance; after a given time t_p', the die was pressed under a given load P' by the ram with discending speed U' until molten aluminum solidified; and a composite material was thus obtained after demolding. These are six parameters Ta', Tf', Tm', Tp', U' and P' as the production conditions for the apparatus. For the purpose of generalizing the production conditions, four parameters were chosen: they are the temperatures of fibers and molten aluminum immediately before mixing: Tf and Ta (hereinafter referred to as "fiber temperature" and "molten metal temperature", respectively); the infiltration speed of molten aluminum U on the surface of a molded fiber; and the squeeze pressure of molten aluminum p. The values of U and p were calculated from the following equations:

Table 2 Physical properties of molten aluminum

Specific gravity	660°C	2.38	g/cm ³
	700°C	2.37	g/cm ³
Specific heat	660°C	0.25	cal/(g·deg)
	700°C	0.25	cal/(g·deg)
Latent heat		94.5	cal/g
Viscosity	660°C	4.5	cP
	700°C	2.9	cP
Heat conductivity	700°C	0.247	cal/(s·cm·deg)

$$U = \frac{(\pi/4)d_0^2 U'}{2\pi r_s(1-V_f)l_s} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$p = \frac{P'}{\pi(d_0/2)^2} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where d₀: outside diameter of a metal mold
 r_s: radius of a molded fiber
 l_s: length of a molded fiber
 V_f: volume fraction of fiber
 U': discending speed of a ram
 P': ram load

Micro-structure and tension tests were carried out for the composite material to obtain data for judging the optimum production conditions. The structure was examined under a common optical microscope on the one hand, and through dye penetration failure-detection tests on the other.

The tensile specimen, as shown in Fig.2, was pulled at the speed of 1mm/min by Instron type tester. The fracture surface was observed by a scanning electron microscope in order to check whether or not internal defects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composite Process and Observation of Structures

Figure 3 shows an example of the relations among ram load, ram displacement, thermocouple output and time when the composite material is produced. The displacement of ram proceeds linearly at first, begins to reduce the rate of increase sharply at a point where molten aluminum fills up the cavity, and reaches a constant value at last. The time required for the molded fiber to be filled with molten aluminum is 0.2s if no change occurs in ram speed, and this value dose not seem to much deviate from the curve.

Figure 4 shows a cross-sectional photograph of a composite material in which composite process dose not reach its central part because of the low fiber temperatures (hereinafter referred to as "incomplete composite material").

Figure 4 indicates that molten aluminum infiltrates into the molded fibers generally from there radial direction, and it is allowed to think that the temperature of whole molten aluminum is constant during its infiltration into the molded fibers because of short infiltration time. Figure 5 gives a microphotograph of the composite material in which no minor defects are found (hereinafter referred to as "sound composite material"). Figure 6 shows the results of investigation on the volume fraction of fiber for sound composite material. Repeated measurements gave an average value of 0.4 in the volume fraction.

Effects of Squeeze Pressures

In order to investigate the effects of squeeze pressure on the structure and tensile strength of the composite material, tests were carried out with pressures changed from 100 to 1,000kg/cm². The results of dye penetration failure-detection tests indicated that there was no shrinkage hole and no minor defects under squeeze pressure of 500kg/cm² or over. No defects were observed on the fracture surface due to tension under the squeeze pressure of 500kg/cm², either. This type of squeeze-pressure dependency of defect formation well coincided with the study carried out by Suzuki(7) on molten forging for Al-7%Si alloy.

Figure 7 shows the influence of squeeze pressure on tensile strength and rupture elongation. From the results, it is recognized that squeeze pressures over 250kg/cm² dose not effect on the tensile strength and elongation of the composites.

Effects of Infiltration Speed

The effects of infiltration speed on composite structures and tensile strength were investigated by changing ram speed with the other production conditions kept constant so as to obtain sound composite materials. The results of structure tests indicated that there was no effect on the composite structure. The results of the tention tests are given in a Fig.8, which shows no effect of infiltration speed on tensile strength and rupture elongation.

A change of infiltration speed of molten aluminum flowing through the narrow gaps between fibers may exert an influence on pressures caused hydrodynamically, and so the pressure necessary for infiltration was investigated on the basis of some assumptions. There are four pressure components necessary for pushing molten aluminum into the molded fibers as follows: pressure drop due to viscosity Δp₁; pressure p₂ necessary to give flowing velocity in the radial direction; pressure p₃ required for withstanding the interfacial tention between SiC fibers and molten aluminum; and the internal pressure p₄ within the molded fibers. The pressure drop Δp₁ and the pressure p₂ are closely related to the infiltration speed.

The pressure p₄ may well be considered as nearly zero (p₄≐0), because no voids were found, and neither blisters nor liberation of air was observed upon reheating the composites up to the melting point of aluminum.

In order to calculate Δp₁, the following symbols are additionally used on the assumption that fibers are in zigzag arrangement as shown in Fig.9:

- | | |
|---|---|
| S _s : surface area of molded-fiber | b: pitch between fibers in the direction perpendicular to flow |
| dr: fiber diameter | e: gap between fiber surfaces |
| μ: coefficient of viscosity of molten aluminium | (U _r) _{max} : maximum flowing speed at radius r of molded fibers |
| ν: coefficient of kinematic viscosity of molten aluminium | V _a : molten aluminium volume fed to composite part per unit time |
| R _e : Reynolds number | |
| d _e : equivalent diameter of unit cell | |

With regard to a unit cell, the following equation holds geometrically.

$$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} b^2 V_f = \frac{\pi}{4} d_f^2 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The maximum speed of flow can be estimated from the equation (4).

$$(U_r)_{max} = \frac{V_a}{S_s} \frac{b}{e} \frac{r_s}{r} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

where

$$V_a = (\pi d_0^2 / 4) U'$$

The Reynolds number can then be calculated by using the equation (5).

$$(R_{rr})_{\max} = (U_r)_{\max} \frac{dr}{v} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

If r of 0.01cm, which is satisfactory close to the center of the molded fibers, is adopted and other values are substituted into the equation, $(Re)_{\max}=12$ and $(Re)_{\max}=38$ are obtained for $U'=1.0\text{cm/s}$ and $U' =3.2\text{cm/s}$, respectively, suggesting that molten aluminum infiltrates as a lamina flow.

The pressure Δp_1 at this time can be calculated from the following equation by the reference(8):

$$\Delta p_1 = \frac{53 \mu U_{\max}}{d_0^2} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Since U_{\max} is a function of r as shown in Eq.(4), Δp_1 can be estimated by Eq.(7).

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_1 &= \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{53 \mu U_{\max}}{d_0^2} dr \\ &= \frac{53 \mu}{d_0^2} \frac{V_a}{S_1} \frac{b}{e} r_2 \ln \frac{r_2}{r_1} \dots\dots\dots(7) \end{aligned}$$

When U' equals 1.0cm/s, r_1 is 0.01cm which is satisfactorily close to the center, and other values are substituted into the the equations, Δp_1 is nearly equal to 1.7kg/cm.

Application of the Bernoulli's theory together with the substitution of $U'=1.0\text{cm/s}$ and $r_1=0.01\text{cm}$ into the equations yields $p_2=1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg/cm}^2$, which is negligibly small.

According to K.F.Sahm et al.(9) p_3 corresponds at least to a work resisting capillarity and the following equation is given, with which the authors can agree with them:

$$p_0 \geq \frac{4 \gamma_i}{d_f} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

where, the symbol γ_i represents interfacial tension between a solid and a liquid. As K.F.Sahm et al. give 1450erg/cm² as the interfacial tension between SiC whiskers and 700°C aluminum, $p_3 \geq 4.5\text{kg/cm}^2$ is obtained in this experiment.

The above estimation leads to the assumption that aluminum infiltration pressure is about 6.2kg/cm² when U' equals 1.0cm/s. This infiltration pressure changes little even if U' rises to 3.2cm/s. Therefore, within the scope of this experiment, a change in ram speed causes little change in the hydrodynamic interaction between fibers and molten aluminum, and so the effects of infiltration speeds on the quality of composite materials seem to be little.

Effects of Fiber Temperatures and Molten Metal Temperatures

If fiber temperatures T_f and molten metal temperatures T_a are low, molten aluminum dose not satisfactorily infiltrate into the molded fibers, and thereby incomplete composite materials result. Table 3 shows the ratios of producing sound composite material without incomplete composition part at various production temperatures. The table suggests that the production ratio of composite materials is better when T_f and T_a are higher.

Figure 10 gives the results of tension tests for sound composites of Table 3. Generally, high production temperatures tend to degrade fibers because of active mutual reaction between fibers and molten aluminum. As a scale of measuring the reactions, the total quantity of heat per unit volume of a composite material immediately before infiltration begins, and the optimum production conditions were investigated. The tensile strengths shown in Fig.10 are rearranged in terms of Q , and the results are given in Fig.11. Q is ex-

Table 3 Fraction of sound composites produced by squeeze casing

Molten aluminum temperature T_a °C	Fiber temperature T_f °C			
	280	370	460	550
660		1/6	2/9	10/10
700	0/3	0/7	2/10	7/7
740		2/8	4/10	10/10
760			6/10	6/6

Numerator: the number of sound composites
Denominator: the total number of squeeze-cast composites

pressed by the following equation:

$$Q = V_f \gamma_f C_{pf} T_f + (1 - V_f) \gamma_a C_{pa} T_a \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

where γ_f , γ_a , specific weights of fibers and molten aluminum, respectively.

Figure 11 suggests that tensile strength may be roughly rearranged in terms of Q. Although it is still difficult to know, from the above results, the value of Q as the optimum production condition, at least it can be said that a value of 355cal/cm³ or less is preferable for SiC fiber-aluminum systems.

Let us consider now solidification layers, which will be formed on fiber surfaces, and there thickness. The calculation of times required heat-exchange between fiber and molten aluminum is of order of 10⁻⁵ sec based on the Heisler diagram, so the heat exchange time is neglected. If the solidification layer is considered to appear as shown in Fig.12 with time neglected, the following two assumptions can be given.

Case 1: After fibers and molten aluminum are mixed, the mixed body reaches a constant temperature Tn. When Tn is lower than the aluminum solidifying point of 660°C, molten aluminum forms solidification layers by releasing latent heat.

Case 2: After mixing, only a given amount of molten aluminum contacting with the surface of fibers solidifies and heats the fibers up to 660°C, while the rest of molten aluminum keeps its initial temperature.

Case 1 seems to be roughly applicable to the case where fibers come in contact with stagnant molten aluminum, while Case 2 dose to the moment when fast flowing molten aluminum comes in contact with fibers. From the heat balance, the following equations are easily obtained for each case:

for Case 1;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & \frac{\pi}{4} (d_{f1}^2 - d_f^2) L_a T_a + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} b^2 (1 - V_f) C_{pa} T_a (T_a - T_m) = \frac{\pi}{4} d_f^2 \gamma_f C_{pf} (T_f - T_m) \\ e_{s1} = b - d_{f1} = b - d_f \sqrt{\frac{C_{pf} \gamma_f (T_f - T_m) + (1 - 1/V_f) C_{pa} T_a (T_a - T_m)}{L_a T_a} + 1} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

for Case 2;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & \frac{\pi}{4} (d_{f2}^2 - d_f^2) (C_{pa} (T_a - T_m) + L_a) \gamma_a = \frac{\pi}{4} d_f^2 \gamma_f C_{pf} (T_m - T_f) \\ e_{s2} = b - d_{f2} = b - d_f \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_f C_{pf} (T_m - T_f)}{C_{pa} (T_a - T_m) + L_a} \gamma_a + 1} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

where Tm: solidifying point of aluminum

La: latent heat of solidifying aluminum

Fig.13 shows the relationships between the solidified surface distance and the production ratio of composite material by substituting all values of Ta and Tf in the production tests into Eqs. (10) and (11). Figure 13 indicates that the narrower the solidified surface gap is, the lower is the production ratio of composite material, and that, in view of qualitative tendency, wider solidified surface gaps of a given value or more are needed to obtain 100% production ratio of composite material. Taking into account the fact that the given value is used as a scale in factories for determining production temperatures, e_{s2} is more convenient than e_{s1} because of the former's better correlation with the production ratio of composite material.

From the above mentioned results, the optimum production temperature lie in the hatched range in Fig.14.

Effect of Copper Addition to Matrix Aluminum

Figure 15 shows the effect of copper addition to matrix on the tensile strength of the composites. A small amounts of copper addition strengthen the composite. As the contribution of matrix strength to the composites strength is so small, it is seemed that copper on the fiber surface depress the harmful reaction between fiber and molten aluminum.

CONCLUSION

Squeeze casting makes it possible to produce the sound composites in an exactly short time.

Under a selective manufacturing condition, the composites of SiC fiber-reinforced aluminum containing a little amount of copper showed as much strength as ROM-predicted.

The effects of the process variables are as follows:

- (1) No micro-cavities is observed under the squeeze pressure of 500kg/cm² or over.
- (2) Infiltration speed does not affect the microstructures and tensile strength.
- (3) There exists an optimum temperature range to fabricate the sound and high strength composite. The range is given by considering both the limited amount of heat quantity and the minimum gap between solidified surface.

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Fig.1 Outline of apparatus

Fig.2 Tensile specimen

Fig.3 An example of time charts

Fig.4 Macroscopic views of incomplete composites ($p=1000 \text{ kg/cm}^2$, $U'=1.0 \text{ cm/s}$, $T_a=660^\circ\text{C}$ for a), 700°C for b), $T_f=370^\circ\text{C}$ for a), 25°C for b)).

Fig.5 Microphotograph of the Composites

Fig.6 Distribution of volume fractions of fiber

Fig.7 Effect of squeeze pressure

Fig.8 Effect of infiltration speed

Fig.9 Model of fiber arrangement and unit cell

Fig.10 Effect of temperatures T_a and T_f

Fig.11 Effect of total heat

Fig.12 Model of solidified layer

Distance between solidified surfaces μm

Fig.13 Relation between solidified surface gap and production ratio of composites

Fig.14 Optimum temperature range for production

Fig.15 Effect of copper addition to matrix